

Studies on Dithiocarbamates. Part XV. Ni(II) and Co(II) Complexes of 3-Phenyl-5-(*o*-hydroxy phenylazo-)rhodanine

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Received 18 August, 1971

It was reported¹ earlier that 3-phenyl-5-(*o*-hydroxyphenylazo-) rhodanine (I) readily forms a fairly stable 1 : 1-complex of copper under weakly acidic conditions with λ_{\max} at 535 $m\mu$. It would, therefore, be interesting to examine the behaviour of the same ligand with respect to other metals like Ni, Co, Fe, Cr and V. To this end our results clearly demonstrate that the ligand readily forms intensely coloured nickel and cobalt complexes, but our failure to detect the formation of any complex over a wide range of *pH* (3–11) with the remaining three metals was very surprising. This is perhaps associated with unfavourable stereochemistry of the complexes with the above three metals.

EXPERIMENTAL

Reagents : Reagents used were of AR-grade. Conductivity water was prepared in an all glass apparatus and in all cases freshly distilled water (alkaline permanganate) was used. Methanol was fractionated over metallic sodium. The metallic salts were $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Methods : Complexation was studied by spectrophotometric method using either Hilger UVISPEK or Hilger recording spectrophotometer in 1 cm. quartz cells at $25^\circ \pm 1$. Experiments were always run in 1 : 1-methanol-water mixture (v/v) against freshly prepared reagent blanks. *pH* values were maintained constant with suitable buffers (phosphate or borate) and the ionic-strength was held constant at 0.04 (KCl).

Stock solutions of the ligand ($1.185 \times 10^{-4}M$) was prepared in acetone-free methanol while the aqueous solutions of the salts were standardised by edta titration². Aliquots of the salt solutions were then diluted to obtain $4.74 \times 10^{-4}M$ solutions. Stoichiometry of the complexes were determined by Job's method³ of continuous variation as well as by mole-ratio method⁴.

Ni (II) formed a single complex with λ_{\max} at 550 $m\mu$ and its stoichiometry was determined at *pH* 8.05 and at 550 $m\mu$ in methanol-water mixture using both equimolar and non-equimolar solutions. Similarly the cobalt complex gave a single peak at 555 $m\mu$ and the experiments were performed at *pH* 9.0.

For the determination of composition by mole-ratio method, a series of solutions were prepared from equimolar solutions of ligand and the metal where the mole ratio of the ligand to metal were varied from 1 : 0.1 to 1 : 4.8.

Stability constants of the complexes were calculated from optical density data following the methods of Job³ and that of Joe and Jones⁴. Since cobalt was found to react in the ratio of 1 : 2, the corresponding formation constant (K) can be derived from the following expression

and

$$K = \frac{x}{(a-x)(b-2x)^2},$$

where x is the concentration of the complex at equilibrium, a and b are the initial of the metal and the ligand respectively. Taking two solutions with identical optical densities (hence the same value of x) we have,

$$K = \frac{x}{(a-x)(b-2x)^2} = \frac{x}{(a'-x)(b'-2x)^2}$$

It is thus possible to evaluate K with known values of the reactants.

The magnitude of K could also be calculated from the mole-ratio curve from the calculated degree of dissociation (α) of the complex. In the case of cobalt complex, the following relation holds good

$$K = \frac{(1-\alpha)}{4\alpha^3 C^2}$$

where C is the concentration of the complex. The degree of dissociation is given by,

$$\alpha = (E_m - E_s)/E_m,$$

where E_m is the optical density with excess of the reagent and E_s is the corresponding value at equivalence point.

As nickel forms 1 : 1-complex, the corresponding expressions for the stability constant are

$$K = \frac{x}{(a-x)(b-x)},$$

and

$$K = \frac{1-\alpha}{\alpha^2 C}$$

The free-energy of formation (ΔG) has also been calculated from the relation,

$$\Delta G = -RT \ln K$$

DISCUSSION

Nickel complex: Application of Vosburg and Cooper's method⁵ demonstrated the formation of a single complex with λ_{\max} at 550 μ . The complex is readily formed under nearly neutral condition with optimum pH around 8 in 1 : 1methanol-water mixture.

Maximum intensity of the colour was attained in about 20 min., but the complex is relatively unstable to the extent that intensity of the colour gradually diminishes after about 30 min.

As stated above, the stoichiometry of the above complex by either method of investigation was found to be 1 : 1, and the corresponding values for $\log K$ were 5.34 and 5.35. The free energy of formation was found to be -7.3 Kcal/mole at 25° corresponding to average $\log K = 5.35$.

Cobalt complex : Using similar technique as above, cobalt chloride also indicated the formation of a single complex (1 : 2) with λ_{\max} at $555 \text{ m}\mu$. In this instance, complexation occurred more readily over a wide range of pH (5 to 11), but the optimum range was found to be 7.0 to 9.4; and the reaction was almost complete in about 20 min at pH around 9. Hence subsequent studies were conducted at pH 9.

In contrast to the Ni-complex, Co-complex was very stable and the fall off in absorbance was negligible over 24 hr when the pH of the system was weakly acidic or nearly neutral. The stability constant of the complex by the above two methods was found to be $\log K = 11.27$ and 11.46 giving an average value of $\log K = 11.37$ and $\Delta G = -15.45$ Kcal/mole and this is twice as much as that found with the Ni-complex.

However, as the compounds were not isolated in crystalline forms, it is difficult to make any definite structural assignment or to offer any specific reason for the observed difference in stability constants. At the same time, it is also known⁶ that cobalt (II) possesses more unpaired electrons in 3d orbital compared to Ni (II) which may affect their configuration and hence the stability constants for the same ligand.

The above results in combination with our earlier report¹ tentatively suggest that the ligand might be an useful reagent for the estimation of cobalt in the presence of other metals.

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